

**Bayesian Phylogenetic Analysis on multi-core Compute
Architectures: Implementation and evaluation of BEAGLE to native
MPI in RevBayes**

Supporting Information

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S1 Speedup by MCMC iteration

Figure S1: Evaluation of the impact of number of MCMC iteration on the speedup of using RevBayes+BEAGLE vs. RevBayes. The results show some stochasticity but now obvious impact of running the MCMC longer on the overall speedup. Thus, our experiments with 10 iterations should be meaningful for any number of MCMC iterations and can be extrapolated.

S2 Validation of the three different implementations: RevBayes, RevBayes+BEAGLE and RevBayes+MPI

Figure S2: Validation of the implementation of the three different likelihood implementations: RevBayes (solid gray line), RevBayes+BEAGLE ('+') and RevBayes+MPI ('o'). We performed three MCMC runs under the same model and datasets (left DNA; right amino acid) and only varied the likelihood implementation. Since the likelihood implementation should not effect the actual likelihood of the model parameters, only the speed of computations and memory requirement, the MCMC runs should produce identical traces, as can be seen here.

S3 Validation of the different partial likelihood storing approaches

Figure S3: Validation of the implementation of different partial likelihood storing approaches in RevBayes. We performed three MCMC runs under the same model and datasets (left DNA; right amino acid) and only varied the option in RevBayes how partial likelihoods are stored (*branch*, *node*, *both*). Since the partial likelihood storing should not effect the actual likelihood of the model parameters, only the speed of computations and memory requirement, the MCMC runs should produce identical traces, as can be seen here.

S4 Validation of the partial likelihood rescaling techniques

Figure S4: Validation of the implementation of different partial likelihood rescaling approaches in *RevBayes*. We performed four MCMC runs under the same model and datasets (left DNA; right amino acid) and only varied the option in *RevBayes* how partial likelihoods are rescaled (*node-joint*, *node-per-cat*, *threshold-joint* and *threshold-per-cat*). Since the partial likelihood rescaling should not effect the actual likelihood of the model parameters, only the speed of computations, the MCMC runs should produce identical traces, as can be seen here.

Figure S5: Validation of the implementation of the partial likelihood rescaling based on the node frequency in *RevBayes*. We performed four MCMC runs under the same model and datasets (left DNA; right amino acid) and only varied the option in *RevBayes* how often the partial likelihoods are rescaled (1 (every node), 8, 65 and 512). Since the partial likelihood rescaling should not effect the actual likelihood of the model parameters, only the speed of computations, the MCMC runs should produce identical traces, as can be seen here.

References